

TECHNIQUES, STRATEGIES FOR GIVING AN EFFECTIVE FEEDBACK

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Annotation: This article is mainly based on the techniques and strategies of giving effective feedback. The process of teaching and training learners on the basis of all complex skills is both time-consuming and has many responsibilities through the improvement of student's awareness. There are many techniques and strategies for the foreign language teachers. Feedback is one of them, it means special attention and evaluation to a particular student for his or her job. It matches specific descriptions and suggestions with a students work.

Key words: reinforcement, punishment, echoing, questioning, stating question, mode, audience.

Introduction:

It is known that feedback is an important formative assessment process to give information to teachers and students about how they are doing relative to classroom goals. According to Susan M. Brookhart (2010) formative assessment includes having clear learning aims, crafting clear lessons and assignments that communicate those targets to students, and usually after giving good feedback helping learners to master how to formulate new goals themselves and action plans will lead to achievement of those goals. Feedback can be very powerful way of teaching together with assessing at the same time. If it is done well it helps to develop evaluated skills of the students. It is not just for assessing or criticizing the learners but can be cognitive and motivational factor for the language learners. Cognitive function of feedback is to enable students comprehend their mistake and be informed how to copy with it. When they understand what is wrong with their work they will try to

develop their poorer skills firstly. Motivational factor is given by the teacher to inform that the learner is working well on the sphere. Satisfaction of their job will lead the students to study more on their own. Furthermore, an effective feedback should contain information about how to be able to correct mistake and work on the work. Students can not hear something beyond their comprehension; nor can they hear something if they are not listening or are feeling like it would be useless to listen to. Whether teachers are giving formal or informal feedback, there are a number of basic principles to keep in mind.

1. Given feedback should be provided only when asked to do so or when your offer is accepted.
2. Feedback is to be given as soon after the event as possible or else it may lose its value.
3. Positive opinions should be presented first
4. Feedback is advised to be given privately if it is possible, especially more negative feedback.
5. 1. Susan M. Brookhart (2010). Educational Measurement: issues and practice, a journal of the National Council on Measurement in education p 55-87.
6. Feedback needs to be part of the overall communication process and 'developmental dialogue'. Use skills such as rapport or mirroring, developing respect and trust with the learner.
7. Teachers should stay in the 'here and now', don't bring up old concerns or previous mistakes, it is not suggested unless this is to highlight a pattern of behaviors.
8. Focusing on behaviors that can be changed individually not personality traits is more preferable.
9. Teachers should talk about and describe specific behaviors, giving examples where possible and it is not effective to evaluate or assume motives.

10. Use 'I' and give your experience of the behavior it is more sensible way of getting closer to your students and their atmosphere. ('When you said..., I thought that you were...').

11. When giving negative feedback, suggest alternative behaviors. It helps students to know another way of behaving which is useful for them to be acquainted with well-built cognitive function.

12. Feedback is for the recipient, not the giver – so it should be sensitive to the impact of teachers' message.

13. Considering the content of the message is important, the process of giving feedback and the congruence between your verbal and non-verbal messages should be motivated.

14. Teacher should encourage reflection. This will involve posing open questions such as:

Did the feedback go as planned? Why or why not?

If you were doing it again what would you do the same next time and what would you do differently? Why? How do you think the patient felt? What makes you think that? What did you learn from this session?

15. Professional feedback givers should be clear about what they are giving feedback on and link this to the learner's overall professional development or intended program outcomes.

Feedback can be understood a way of conveying the message towards the correction of mistake. Showing incorrectness is useful in giving feedback to the learners if they are used appropriately: this can be done in a number of different ways: repeating, echoing, statement and question, expression.

Repeating: teacher may ask the student to repeat what they have said, perhaps by saying Again. It should be with intonation and expression in order to indicate that something isn't clear to teacher or there is problem with the task or speech.

Echoing: it is a simple way of pin-pointing an error done by the performer. Repetition of what the student has said. Emphasizing the part of the sentence which gone wrong.

Expression: when language trainer knows the class well, facial expression or a gesture (for example, a wobbling hand) may be enough to indicate that something belongs to the work by students doesn't quite work. This way needs to be done with careful attention as the wrong expression or gesture can be appeared to be mocking or cruel. A quick way of helping students to activate rules they already know is to give a quick hint. Teacher might just say the word rather than the present perfect. Or they could say countable to make them think about a concord mistake they have made, or tell to indicate they have chosen the wrong use to make them think that perhaps they should have used the past simple instead of present perfect. This kind of hinting depends upon the students and the teacher sharing metalanguage (linguistic terms) to correct themselves which, occurs during the class.

According to the research on the studies of giving feedback was risen 100 years ago. It was called as behaviorism (Thorndike, 1913). It was divided into two types: Positive feedback used to the students who accomplished the task well and it was seen as an example to the other students of the class. Negative feedback was given to the ones who could not do their task effectively or satisfactorily. Negative feedback was estimated to be punishment for most of time. It happened to be challenging situation for the learners if it is given them in front of the class. Both of them, reinforcement and punishment effected to the students' learning. Until recent time it was not learned individually out of the classroom. Recent studies have showed that there are some techniques of feedback in teaching.

Effective types of feedback can divided into these types:

Appreciation.

First way is considered to be far more impressive than the others. Appreciation is the most effective and important means of giving feedback. It is also called as a "feedback door." It begins with thanking students for submitting their work, which

really vital step to start the assessment towards the completion of the learners tasks, then it acknowledges and validates their time spent learning something new. Appreciation comments do not have to be drawn out all the time in order to have a positive impact. They can be as delivered simply as by saying “thank you for sharing this awesome suggestion or idea with us. Receiving a positive, appreciative comment at the outset, students are more likely to feel respected and engage with any additional feedback provided by their teachers.

Sayback is known from the name which involves restating what learners have said. This method shows learners that their posts were read and it lets them know that they are moving on the right track. Often, the best way to begin this method a sayback comment is used with an “I agree” or some other appreciative statement. For instance “I agree with your conclusion, it was done on topic and with careful attention. It should be done by saying the name of an internet link or sharing it to a resource extends learning beyond the course content and introduces learners to new information, ideas, perspectives, and digital tools. Such as by stating that, one of our course members introduced a participant to a new creative commons resource by writing the following:

“The creativity and learning capacity depend on the teacher’s using feedback on time”.

Mode of feedback.

Feedback can be delivered in many modalities. Some of them are delivered in oral form whereas others are better in a written form. Observing the situation and give a quick correction to the made mistake seems better than observing the progress and not to evaluate the learner’s problem in studying. Peter Johnston, an author of “Choice words” (2004) discussed how to ask questions while giving oral evaluation. Decision of choosing what type of feedback to give highly depends on the students’ age and reading ability. Especially for the learners who are young and unable to depict the meaning of feedback. A good choice of mode can be brief, could initiate

a helpful, friendly conversation with the student and teacher. Bad choice of mode is to write things which are difficult for the learners to comprehend.

Audience

Is the next strong requirement from the teachers. It also works with best when it has a meaningful and appropriate sense of the audience. Feedback about the specifics of individual work is addressed to the individual student, in terms the student can understand. It is done with the purpose that, the teacher gave attention to the work based learning of his or her learner. If the same message is intended to deliver it is more beneficial for the teachers, because the same mistake by all students does not take much time to explain. The purposes of feedback audience are:

- to reach the appropriate students with specific feedback
- to communicate with the learners in order to make them feel that their work is evaluated.

By providing feedback and providing with relevant choices to them to delve their mistake or misconception well the process of assessment can be made easier.

Conclusion.

Giving good feedback is a skill that requires practice. There have been presented techniques, and choices about feedback strategies and content most likely to give students the information they need to improve and the motivation to use.

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